

Student's Language Problems in Communicating during Learning

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to reveal students' language problems in communicating during learning. This research uses qualitative research with grounded theory type. The data of this research are in the form of words and sentences. The results of the study illustrate that the problems of speaking Indonesian during the teaching and learning process are caused by a lack of awareness of students to use Indonesian, so that there is a lack of knowledge about vocabulary in Indonesian. In this case, the teacher plays a very important role in guiding them to get to know the Indonesian language first. In the context of education, language has an important role because of its potential impact on student achievement when exposed to a particular teaching program.

INTRODUCTION

Communication education, language consists of two types, namely, spoken and written. Both parts are composed of a series of letters to form a word and sentence. This has been stated by Tarigan (2008) that writing is a language skill to communicate indirectly, not face to face between the author and the reader, only the author's writing is a means of communication to convey the intent and purpose to the reader. In addition, language is often used in social relations through interactions which are considered as a means of communication between one individual and another. is the process of delivering information, ideas, and messages from Natural language communication has long been considered a hallmark of human intelligence (Ammanabrolu&Ried, 2021). Language is an alternative means of communication and is closely related to everyday life. In Indonesian language.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

One person to another or a group. The occurrence of communication is triggered by the interdependence of information, so that good communication is established through media such as social media or directly orally. Building good interactions through communication can strengthen a relationship, but if the interactions are based on conflict and the pros and cons will break a relationship between groups or communities. This opinion is in line with Widjaja (2002) which states that communication is the core of all social relations, if someone holds social relations through communication, then the communication system becomes a determinant that can unite or solve a communication relationship between the group. In addition, continuous communication with the world of education, such as the process of learning and teaching in the school environment.

The process of learning and teaching is included in instrumental communication. In this case, it requires teachers, namely teachers, not only to distribute knowledge to be absorbed by students, but also to educate students to form a noble attitude and foster self-confidence to mentally weak students. Teaching and learning activities involve teachers and students directly as a communication tool to respond to the interlocutor.

Currently, language problems are starting to appear among students, this is triggered by environmental conditions that cultivate regional languages while Indonesian is neglected. Schools located in rural areas more often use local languages, both in their daily environment at home and in the school environment. In essence, Indonesian language should be applied in the school environment, but some teachers ignore this. According to them, where the two feet stand, that's where the local language is upheld. So that over time, students

begin to feel foreign to Indonesian and have difficulty communicating. During the learning and teaching process, students who are usually active in the classroom become passive. This happens because they understand what the teacher is saying, but are confused about how to respond.

Language errors are a big challenge for educators who hold Indonesian language lessons. In order to maintain the integrity of the Indonesian language so that it is not forgotten, the teacher must familiarize his students with listening or communicating using Indonesian when learning takes place. If you get used to it continuously, Indonesian errors can be overcome.

Based on the background that has been described, the formulation of the problem in this study are the factors that cause language problems in communicating with students during learning and solutions to overcome these problems so that the integrity of the Indonesian language is maintained.

Basically, the purpose of this paper is to obtain accurate results and be adapted to the problems in the research. The purpose of this study is to explain the causes of errors in communicating to students during the learning and teaching process.

METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative method. According to Creswell (2016) qualitative research is a type of research that explores and understands the meaning of a number of individuals or groups of people who come from social problems, usually this research is guided by people's lives, namely the state of the social environment, history, behavior, and phenomena that occur in the environment. Public. In this case, the author tries to understand and interpret an event in Indonesian language interaction among upper secondary level students which aims to solve the problem to find a bright spot to overcome it. Therefore, the author uses a qualitative research type grounded theory.

According to Martin and Turner (1986) the grounded theory approach is a general methodology of analysis related to systematic data collection, using a series of methods to produce an inductive theory about the substantive area. So, the grounded theory method is guided by empirical studies obtained when entering the field so as to obtain a conceptual theory.

The steps taken by the author to obtain a conceptual theory by collecting data according to what is happening in the field are then processed and analyzed scientifically. Researchers make observations first by conducting social interactions such as interviews and observing conditions that occur in the field, these actions obtain data from the object being interviewed. Then the data is analyzed into concepts and hypotheses based on the data obtained, so as to produce a theory from the data.

RESULTS

The problem of language errors in communication during the teaching and learning process raises a big question mark, why this can happen. Isn't school a place for education and Indonesian is often used in the educational aspect? Therefore, the authors conducted research by making students as objects through the interview method and in writing between students and writers by distributing essay questions. So that the data collected as follows.

Code Subject	Question	Results
1. MA	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How important is Indonesian in your life? 2. Have you used Indonesian language in your daily life? 3. What are your obstacles during the Indonesian language learning process? 	<p>Indonesian is the main language, so it is very important in life.</p> <p>Seldom.</p> <p>Not fast enough to understand.</p>
2. NH	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How important is Indonesian in your life? 2. Have you used Indonesian language in your daily life? 3. What are your obstacles during the Indonesian language learning process? 	<p>Indonesian is the main and important language for daily interaction.</p> <p>Seldom.</p> <p>It's hard to understand.</p>
3. TA	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How important is Indonesian in your life? 2. Have you used Indonesian language in your daily life? 3. What are your obstacles during the Indonesian language 	<p>Indonesian is important because it is used to communicate.</p> <p>Seldom.</p> <p>Not understood.</p>

	learning Process	
4. IR	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How important is Indonesian in your life? 2. Have you used Indonesian language in your daily life? 3. What are your obstacles during the Indonesian language learning process? 	<p>Indonesian is important for daily conversation with teachers, friends and parents.</p> <p>Rarely.</p> <p>Difficult to understand.</p>
5. DA	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How important is Indonesian in your life? 2. Have you used Indonesian language in your daily life? 3. What are your obstacles during the Indonesian language learning process? 	<p>Indonesian is the language of our unity, so it is important in everyday life.</p> <p>Seldom.</p> <p>Understand when explained, but hard to rephrase.</p>
6. MA	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How important is Indonesian in your life? 2. Have you used Indonesian language in your daily life? 3. What are your obstacles during the Indonesian language learning process? 	<p>It is very important because Indonesian is the language of our unity, so it is important in everyday life.</p> <p>Bit by bit.</p> <p>Understand when explained, but hard to explain again.</p>

7. SF	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How important is Indonesian in your life? 2. Have you used Indonesian language in your daily life? 3. What are your obstacles during the Indonesian language learning process? 	<p>It is important because it is made the language of unity.</p> <p>Not.</p> <p>Little understanding.</p>
8. IS	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How important is Indonesian in your life? 2. Have you used Indonesian language in your daily life? 3. What are your obstacles during the Indonesian language learning process? 	<p>Indonesian is the language of unity, so it is important in everyday life.</p> <p>Not.</p> <p>Got it, but it's hard to rephrase.</p>
9. MF	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How important is Indonesian in your life? 2. Have you used Indonesian language in your daily life? 3. What are your obstacles during the Indonesian language learning process? 	<p>Very important.</p> <p>Never.</p> <p>A little hard to understand.</p>
10. KN	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How important is Indonesian in your life? 2. Have you used Indonesian language in your daily life? 3. What are your obstacles during the 	<p>Important, because the language of unity and is used in everyday life.</p> <p>Not.</p> <p>Time is explained hard to understand.</p>

	Indonesian language learning process?	
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DISCUSSION

Richards, Platt, and Weber (1985:153) state that language is a human communication system which is expressed through the arrangement of sounds or written expressions that are structured to form larger units, such as morphemes, words, and sentences. This is in line with the reality that occurs, language is the most important component in human life. The importance of a language can be felt starting from the opening of both eyes in the morning until late at night, all of that can not be separated from the communication system that aims to express an idea to be conveyed to the other person through interaction. Even so, errors in language do not escape when interacting with the interlocutor both in groups and individually through communication.

According to Rakhmat (1998:1), communication is considered a fundamental social process in human life who wishes to maintain an agreement on various social rules through communication. The theory put forward by Rakhmat is in line with Richards, communication is a process of expressing something orally which aims to express ideas, regarding various matters of social and political rules. Considering that humans are social creatures and thirst for education, therefore language becomes a means of blending.

The world of education is closely related to the scope of learning that involves communication. This was stated by Knirk and Gustafson (1986:5), stating that learning is a systematic process through the stages of design, implementation, and evaluation. In this case, it is in line with Dimiyati and Mujino (1999:297) who argue that learning is a teacher activity programmed in instructional design to make students learn actively and emphasizes the provision of learning resources. An active and programmed learning process can be realized because the teacher becomes the operationalization that carries out learning, so that communication between teachers and students is established through interaction. However, the learning process becomes hampered, when the teacher teaches learning using Indonesian while the students respond using the local language.

This problem occurred to the students of SMA N I Peudada when learning Indonesian took place. When teachers explain learning materials to students, most of them have difficulty understanding and are slow to respond. Even students often argue using the local language. In essence, when learning takes place, there will usually be a reciprocal relationship between the two directions, namely the teacher and the student, but this reciprocal relationship will not be

synchronous if the student and teacher use a different language. Therefore, learning is a process of educative interaction between teachers and students by involving language through communication tools. In the community and becomes an alternative in taking education.

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Indonesian language errors in communicating are in the form of deviations from the use of Indonesian verbally and in writing that deviate from linguistic rules or rules, (Setyawati: 2010). The problems that occur in the field are mainly due to the location of the school in a rural area, plus 99% of the environmental conditions using the local language. As a result, students in the local area are comfortable with the Acehese language and think that Indonesian is not too important. Then students do not understand the rules of language, even their tongues feel foreign when a series of Indonesian sentences come out of their lips.

Ariningsih, Sumarwati, and Saddono (2012) state that language errors that often occur among students are spelling errors, diction errors, sentence errors, and paragraph errors. This statement is in accordance with what happened in the field, when the teacher assigned students to compose an

essay in the form of a narrative. Students experience problems in terms of composing sentences even though the teacher has explained the systematics in the preparation of narrative essays. It turns out that the student's problem is not in the technique of compiling the narrative essay, but the lack of vocabulary and lack of reading.

It can be concluded that the problems of speaking Indonesian during the teaching and learning process are caused by a lack of awareness of students to use Indonesian, so that there is minimal knowledge of Indonesian vocabulary. In addition, students also find it difficult to complete assignments as described by Ariningsih, Sumarwati, and Saddono (2012).

Based on the author's observations, the problem of language errors in communication to students during the teaching and learning process can be overcome, so that the reciprocal relationship between teachers and students can be well established. In this case, it requires the role of a teacher to guide students to know the Indonesian language first, things that can overcome these problems, namely:

- a) The teacher first introduces standard and non-standard words and linguistic rules according to their level of education.
- b) Applying Indonesian when teaching and familiarizing students with responding in Indonesian too.
- c) Train students to speak Indonesian through practical assignments or presenting their work in front of the class, while other students give their feedback.

If these three things are continuously applied to students, then these problems can be solved. Communication can be established properly and according to linguistic rules, so as to maintain the integrity of the Indonesian language and avoid language errors.

CONCLUSIONS

Language becomes a communication tool to connect one individual to another, channel information and implement a behavior or action. Language has its own characteristics, both regional and Indonesian. Those who maintain the integrity of their local language and forget their unified language, so that the problem of errors in communication arises among students during the teaching and learning process. Every problem has a solution, one of which is introducing standard and non-standard words and language rules, getting used to using Indonesian during learning, and training students to speak Indonesian through practical assignments or

presentations in front of other students.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so that research still needs to be done on the following titles "Student's Language Problems in Communicating during Learning."

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